

Project Deliverable D-JRP17- WP7.Del2

Workpackage 7

Responsible Partner: ANSES

Contributing partners: APHA, FLI, IZSAM,
INIAV, INSA, IZS, WBVR

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Project deliverable	D-JRP17-WP7.Del2: Final draft of data management plan
Project Acronym	JRP17-ET2.1-IDEMBRU
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Due month of the report	48
Actual submission month	55
Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R Save date: 10-Apr-23
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU This is the default setting. If this project deliverable should be confidential, please add justification here (may be assessed by PMT):
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	<p>OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Communication Team <input type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/> EEA <input type="checkbox"/> EMA <input type="checkbox"/> FAO <input type="checkbox"/> WHO <input type="checkbox"/> OIE <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Other international stakeholder(s):</p> <p>Social Media:</p> <p>Other recipient(s):</p>

DELIVERABLE REPORT D-JRP17-WP7.DEL2: FINAL DRAFT OF DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

Description of the task

The main components of the toolkit will be made available as open resources on a European website together with standard operating procedures, scientific papers and conference contributions. A notification system including emerging *Brucella* will be achieved to track and collect epidemiological and clinical data.

Confidential. A part of ANSES server has been opened for the members of IDEMBRU consortium. This will serve to store large data files – DNA sequences, data bases, epidemiological questionnaires and results provided by WP3, WP4, and WP5. The data storage space is divided according to the workpackage needs. All data have been stripped of any identifications, both personal identifiers or institutional.